

III INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Nanomaterials and Polymers: Applied Chemistry for Sustainable Development

PROGRAMME AND BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

June 13-14, 2024 Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

**III INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
„Nanomaterials and Polymers:
Applied Chemistry for Sustainable Development“
Programme and Book of Abstracts**

Publisher:

University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics
Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000 Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Tel: +387 51 319 142
<https://pmf.unibl.org/>

Editor:

Suzana GOTOVAC ATLAGIĆ,
Co-chair of the Conference

Technical Editor:

Sanja PRŽULJ,
member of the Organizing committee of the Conference

Cover page:

Sitec d.o.o.

Edition:

1. edition

Scientific committee

Milica Balaban, Bosnia and Herzegovina, President
Branislav Jovančićević, Serbia
Vesna Antić, Serbia
Eyad Khalaf, Egypt
Anita Grozdanov, North Macedonia
Dijana Jelić, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Saša Zeljković, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Matteo Guidotti, Italy
Mariya Nikolova, Bulgaria
Flora Krasniqi, Albania
Lidia Gullon Corral, Spain

Organizing committee

Radoslav Dekić, Chair
Suzana Gotovac Atlagić, Co-chair
Milana Grbić, Co-chair
Goran Trbić
Drago Gverić
Jovana Branković
Sanja Pržulj
Dragana Gajić
Dejana Savić
Mirela Boroja

Greetings from the organizers

Prof. dr Milica BALABAN

President of the NanoPol2024
Scientific Committee

Dear Participants, dear Scientific and Organising Committee members of the NanoPol2024

It is our immense pleasure to wrap up this year edition of the NanoPol as the successful conference and with best impressions. Our journey started at the end of pandemic times. We first held NanoPol2022 under support of the EIT RM-funded project RIS RESTORE in which our Department of Chemistry participated. Although the logistic was hard and even the TV-statements were given under the masks still the atmosphere and the exchange was excellent and we knew immediately that we have hit the jackpot. Our country, although small, is becoming important European industrial hub in material exploitation and processing. We have recognised the need for the highly specialized need for the conference on subjects of nanomaterials and polymers and the scientific/expert's audience recognized that.

Second edition NanoPol 2023 was again in great mood and with diverse subjects, with guests from Japan, Bulgaria, Italy, Spain ... Each year the second day of the conference is based on the industrial visit and the discussions of the realistic problems. We must say that even multiple new project applications were born during these visits.

NanoPol2024, completely evolved into the full-scale international conference according to our scientific legislation and this book of abstracts is the results of it.

We hope you will share our enthusiasm in spreading the word on responsible production of nanomaterials and polymers and see you again at NanoPol2025.

Yours,

Team of students and researchers from the organising team, Chemistry Department, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka, June 13, 2024.

University of Banja Luka
Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics

„Nanomaterials and Polymers:
Applied Chemistry for Sustainable Development“
NanoPol 2024 Conference

Programme

DAY 1 (June 13, 2024)

8.30-9.00 | Registration and media statements

9.00-9.15 | Greetings by host institution and opening by assistant minister of scientific and technological development and higher education, Jelena STARČEVIĆ, PhD

Nanomaterial section

9.15-9.45 (25+5 minutes) | Prof dr Matteo GUIDOTTI
Nanosciences and nanotechnologies: safety concerns, security issues and emerging threats

9.45-10.15 (25+5 minutes) | Prof dr Dragana TOMAŠEVIĆ PILIPOVIĆ
Development of nanomaterials for the treatment of various environmental media

10.15-10.45 (25+5 minutes) | Prof dr Radovan KUKOBAT
Hybrid nanoporous materials for adsorption, molecular separation and biomedical applications

MODERATOR of Nanomaterial section prof dr Vladimiro DAL SANTO

10.45-11.30 | Coffee break with poster session

Polymer section

11.30-12.00 (25+5 minutes) | HYBRID PARTICIPATION
Dr Eyad KHALAF, Cellulosic Polymers: Fundamentals and Advanced Applications

12.00-12.30 (25+5 minutes) | Prof dr Anita GROZDANOV
Eco-friendly polymer composites

12.30-13.00 (25+5 minutes) | Prof dr Miroslav HUSKIĆ, 5-HMF based polymers

MODERATOR of Polymer section prof dr Vladimiro DAL SANTO

13.00 Greetings and closing of the presentation part

13.00-15.00 | Buffet networking lunch, poster observation and evaluation, stand visits (on site)

14.30 | Announcement of the best poster, memorial pictures and prize delivery

DAY 2 (June 14, 2024)

8.00-8.15 | Gathering at the parking lot of the Faculty of Natural Sciences (Mladena Stojanovića 2, Banja Luka) limited number of participants

8.15-09.15 | Travel to Prnjavor City

09.30-10.30 | Visit to the city hall, discussion with Mayor, prof dr Darko Tomaš - The entrepreneurship and multiethnic traditions in the city of Prnjavor

11.00-13.00 | visit to the „state-of-the-art“ food packaging company „Mladegspak“ in Prnjavor (deep tech and application of polymers in food industry)

13.00-15.00 | Farewell lunch in Prnjavor City

16.00 | Arrival at the parking lot of the Faculty of Natural Sciences (Mladena Stojanovića 2, Banja Luka)

EIT RawMaterials is supported by the EIT,
a body of the European Union

Table of Contents

Photo gallery from the NanoPol 2024 conference and the study trip	10
PLENARY SECTION NANOMaterials	13
Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies: Safety Concerns, Security Issues and Emerging Threats	14
Development of Nanomaterials for the Treatment of Various Environmental Media	16
Hybrid Nanoporous Materials for Adsorption, Molecular Separation and Biomedical Applications	18
PLENARY SECTION POLYmers	21
Cellulosic Polymers: Fundamentals and Advanced Applications	22
Eco-friendly Polymer Composites	24
5-HMF Based Polymers	26
POSTER SECTION NANOMaterials	29
Application of Pyrophyllite, Titanium Dioxide and UV LED Light for Enhanced Disinfection	30
Diving into the Stabilizing Mechanism of In-promoted Catalysts for the Sustainable Hydrogen Production: A Combined Operando XRD/XAS and Modeling Study	32
Graphene Oxide Membrane for Metal Ion Separation	34
Application of Agro-Industrial Waste for Nanomaterial Synthesis	36
Electron Migration through Nanotubes Induced by Mechanical Deformation	38
Synthesis of Hydrophobic Zeolite from Ugljevik Thermal Power Plant Fly Ash	40
Co-sputtered Cu and Ti Coating in O ₂ Atmosphere	42
The Possibility of Using Nanomaterials for the Remediation of Soil Contaminated with Toxic Metals	44
Green Microemulsion Synthesis of the Manganese Oxide Nanoparticles	46
POSTER SECTION POLYmers	49
Amino-functionalized Glycidyl Methacrylate-based Copolymer as an Effective Sorbent for Anionic Dye from Aqueous Solutions	50
Kaolin from Bosnia and Herzegovina as Potential Material in Synthesis of Geopolymers	52
Separation of Cu-ions from Mixed Polymer Fraction of Recycled Electric Cables	54
The Contribution of Modern Production to the Sustainable Development	56
Decrease in Diameter of Synthetic Fibers as a Threatening Factor in Microplastics Pollution	58

Photo gallery from the NanoPol 2024 conference and the study trip

PLENARY SECTION
NANOmaterials

Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies: Safety Concerns, Security Issues and Emerging Threats

Matteo Guidotti¹, Stefano Econdi¹, Vladimiro Dal Santo¹, Alessandra Rossodivita²

¹CNR-National Research Council, SCITEC-Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies
"Giulio Natta", via C. Golgi 19, Milan, Italy

²ASST Valtellina e Alto Lario - Hospital Complex, Sondrio, Italy

*matteo.guidotti@scitec.cnr.it

ABSTRACT

Should scientist always think of potential illicit use of new discoveries and developments? Are new generations of chemists aware of such intentional misuse? The talk aims at discussing together how an expert should always think of a safe, secure and ethically sound use of nanosciences and nanotechnologies. These disciplines are key resources for the humankind, providing innovative tools and devices also for the detection, protection and decontamination from chemical, biological, radiological or nuclear (CBRN) hazardous materials. At the same time, they may lead to unprecedented weapons and uncontrolled warfare agents, through the synthesis of novel and more effective toxic agents or by improving the production capability of intentionally toxic systems.

Regarding the protection from CBRN hazardous agents, the attention of the literature moved, in last years, from the traditional chemical abatement (requiring huge amounts of solvent and/or reagents) to the catalytic decontamination, based on heterogeneous (solid-liquid or solid-vapour) nanostructured catalysts, which are able to convert highly toxic species into non-toxic secondary products under ambient conditions. Such catalytic systems can work as reactive sorbent materials, as oxidation promoters or as photocatalysts activated by sunlight, finding various 'smart' applications, such as self-decontaminating textiles, skin active-protection creams or detoxifying foams.

Risks and threats to the human health linked to the use of nanosystems will be highlighted too. Some paradigmatic cases will be treated, such as the ubiquitous use of nanosized inorganic oxides in everyday use products, that is attracting an ever-growing attention in terms of health concerns, or the long-term noxious effects nanoparticle debris recorded in conflict areas around the world, where highly energetic depleted uranium-based weaponry was used.

The DeepGreenInno Project under the EU-funded EIT-HEI Initiative is gratefully acknowledged.

Keywords:

nanosystems

toxicological hazard

dual-use chemicals

emerging threats

Development of Nanomaterials for the Treatment of Various Environmental Media

Dragana Tomašević Pilipović^{1*}, Nataša Slijepčević¹, Đurđa Kerkez¹, Jovana Jokić Govedarica¹,
Nataša Duduković¹

Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, Novi Sad, Republika Srbija

*dragana.tomasevic@dh.uns.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

Since the onset of the 21st century, the pace of industrialization and urbanization has surged, ushering in unprecedented convenience alongside profound environmental repercussions. Most of pollution stems from mining, smelting, industrial waste, oil spills, and other human-driven sources, which introduce a plethora of toxic pollutants into the soil, comprising heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, halogenated hydrocarbons, and more. Engineered nanomaterials, with their expansive specific surface areas and distinctive physical and chemical properties, have emerged as promising tools in environmental science. Among these, nano zero valent iron (nZVI) nano zero valent iron (nZVI) has garnered significant research attention due to its exceptional ability to remove pollutants. nZVI is composed of a Fe₀ core and a mixed-valent iron oxide shell of Fe(II) and Fe(III), and is an extension of micron-sized zero-valent iron (mZVI) materials. The borohydride reduction process, however, is hampered by its high cost, the use of toxic NaBH₄, and the production of harmful flammable hydrogen. Nowadays, researchers are increasingly focusing on green synthesis approaches for nZVI, employing environmentally friendly, cost-effective methods with simple operation. This “green” methodology involves polyphenols extracted from various plants (e.g., green tea, oak, mulberry) as reducing agents for iron ions prior to nZVI formation. Numerous endeavours have been made to stabilize environmentally friendly nZVI on various support materials, including clay, bentonite, and biomaterials, aimed at the removal of diverse pollutants. Clays serve as suitable hosts for nZVI, capable of binding contaminants anions or cations through ion exchange or adsorption, owing to their extensive specific surface area and high cation exchange capacity (CEC). Moreover, ions can adhere to the boundaries of clay crystal lattices, exchanging with other ions present in water or sediment. Biochar (BC), with its porous structure, high adsorption capacity, and extensive specific surface area, has increasingly served as a supportive medium for nZVI, bolstering dispersibility. Additionally, immobilization within a support matrix is employed to capitalize on the combined benefits of both components in nZVI-based nanocomposites, often resulting in synergistic effects on pollutant removal.

This paper will raise questions about the feasibility of synthesizing nZVI using various plant-derived materials, supported by native clay and biochar, while assessing its applicability in remediation across varied environmental matrices.

Keywords: synthesis and supporting of nZVI pollution environmental remediation

Acknowledgement: The research was financed by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #7753609, BEuSED.

Hybrid Nanoporous Materials for Adsorption, Molecular Separation and Biomedical Applications

Radovan Kukobat¹

University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Technology, Department of Chemical Engineering and Technology, B.V Stepe Stepanovica 73, Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*radovan.kukobat@tf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

Developing hybrid nanoporous materials with excellent properties such as high specific surface area, mechanical and electrical properties is a challenge of materials science for chemical and biochemical applications. Nanomaterials including graphene, zeolites, nanohydroxyapatites and metal organic frameworks (MOFs) are challenging for the future development of modern society including gas separation for green future, drug delivery and bone implants for advanced biotechnology. This talk gives an overview with the insights to developing of the new class of hybrid materials including graphene, hydroxyapatite, zeolites and MOF with enhanced porosity, sorption and mechanical properties. Graphene is an attractive 2D nanomaterial with theoretical surface area of $2600 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, being widely used in gas separation, adsorption and bioapplications. Graphene combined with zeolites forms 2D nanochannels that can serve for hydrogen separation from light hydrocarbons. An excellent separation efficiency at H_2/CH_4 selectivity of ~ 250 at the permeance of 5.8×10^6 barrer could be achieved through the 2D nanochannels at the graphene-zeolite interface.¹ Also the possible interfacial separation was demonstrated using graphene-hydroxylapatite nanochannels that are promising for H_2/CH_4 separation, reaching the selectivity of ~ 40 at the separation rate as high as 2.4×10^5 barrers.² On the other hand, graphene-nanohydroxyapatite is promising nanoporous material for the bone scaffold fabrication. The graphene-nanohydroxyapatite has excellent mechanical strength as high as 300 MPa, owing to the graphene layers that interconnect the nanohydroxyapatite crystals. Nanoporous materials such as zeolites and MOF are promising for the future development of drug carriers such as letrozole. Letrozole-loaded clinoptilolite zeolites have a high dissolution, showing higher dissolution than pure letrozole.³ This phenomenon occurs due to a uniform layered adsorption of letrozole onto the external surface clinoptilolite zeolite, being accessible to the solvent for dissolution. Positive adsorption energy of 0.02 eV suggests repulsive interactions between clinoptilolite and letrozole, stimulating the desorption process. In addition, MOF such as MOF-5 is very promising for the future enhancement of the dissolution of poorly soluble drugs. MOF-5 has a specific surface area of over $2000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, being promising carrier for adsorption of poorly water-soluble drugs and its dissolution. Hence, this talk will deal with the the fundamental understanding of the properties of nanomaterials including graphene, nanohydroxyapatite, nanoporous clinoptilolite and MOF for the future applications in science and technology.

Keywords: gas separation adsorption porosity drug delivery

1. R. Kukobat, et al., Science Advances 2022, 8, eabl3521; 10.1126/sciadv.abl3521.
2. R. Kukobat, et al., J. Phys. Chem. 2022, 126, 3653–3660; doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.1c08928
3. R. Kukobat, et al., J. Colloid Interface Sci. 2024, 653, 170 – 178; doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2023.08.199.

PLENARY SECTION
POLYmers

HYBRID PARTICIPATION

Cellulosic Polymers: Fundamentals and Advanced Applications

Eyad Sayed Abdallah Khalaf

R&D, Science & Technology Centre of Excellence (STCE) in Cairo, Egypt.

*eyad.s.a.khalaf@stce-egypt.org

ABSTRACT

Recently, natural fibers have attracted the greatest attention of both academic and industrial researchers for being environmentally friendly, biodegradable, and readily available. The valorization of biomass and agro-natural fibers as alternatives to petroleum-based fillers is an uncompromising challenge in present-day rubber research. Sugarcane bagasse (SCB) and rice straw (RS) are two popular types of cellulose-rich natural fiber materials that are preferentially used as alternative fillers in rubber technology.

This scientific research interestingly demonstrates current advances in natural fiber-filled rubber composites in terms of physio-mechanical, thermal, biodegradable, and analytical properties for my recent research. The incorporation of unmodified natural fibers as filler was not adequate to offer the desired reinforcement in rubber composites. However, several surface modification methods could be introduced to improve the overall performance of natural fiber-filled rubber composites, and one of the most environmentally friendly methods was briefly addressed. The most prominent outcomes of the research clarified that the optimum contents that can be incorporated from both SCB and treated RS in a conventional formulation of 40 PHR carbon black (CB)-filled styrene butadiene rubber (SBR) composites are 30 PHR and 20 PHR, respectively. Besides, the variation in the different physico-mechanical and thermal properties was studied and briefly analyzed. The rheological characteristics were found to provide a fingerprint for the formulation processing, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to study the morphology of the fibers inside the rubber matrix. It was also found to be in agreement with and supporting the results of tensile testing.

Moreover, the effect of the two main reinforcing fillers, viz., CB and silica (Si), on the rheological, physico-mechanical, and thermal properties of bagasse-filled SBR (B-SBR) composites was investigated. Overall, CB-filled vulcanizates recorded dominant mechanical properties compared to the Si-filled B-SBR vulcanizates. Both fillers offered a noticeable improvement in thermal stability, but with a preference for the silica-filled compounds. This study summarizes a detailed discussion of the emerging green technologies for tire production.

One more study evaluates the extraction process of sugarcane bagasse (SCB) celluloses with an alkali treatment method, aided by an optimization for the obtained results by using the response surface methodology (RSM) as a statistical method for modelling and analyzing the process. The effects of three significant process parameters, namely temperature, reaction time, and sodium hydroxide concentration, on the yield of extracted cellulose are investigated with the aid of Design of Experiment (DOE) software. The Box-Behnken design with the three optimal processing independent variables was used to calculate the ideal conditions for extracting cellulose from SCB. The X-ray diffractometer (XRD) analyses recorded an increase in crystallinity for the extracted cellulose compared to the raw bagasse fibers, and the XRD analysis was found to be in complete agreement with the findings of the Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis.

All in all, these recent research studies clarify the present status and future prospects of natural fiber incorporation in a diversity of engineering and industrial applications. The successful design of natural fiber-based sustainable rubber composites can introduce a new era in green rubber technology.

Keywords: cellulose response surface methodology sustainable rubber composites green rubber technology

Eco-friendly Polymer Composites

Anita Grozdanov

Department of Organic Technologies, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University Ss Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, Rugjer Boksovici 16, 1000 Skopje, R. N. Macedonia

*anita@tmf.ukim.edu.mk

ABSTRACT

Last decades, sustainable development becomes a key point for almost all human activities. The concept of "green" development correlates design practices, materials and energy resources to other aspects of sustainability. Buildings that integrate principles of sustainability into design and construction strive towards maximum energy efficiency, a minimization of the use of virgin renewable and non-renewable resources, the elimination of toxicity from building structures and processes, the reduction of CO₂ equivalent emissions, and waste minimization. The consistent use of construction materials that meet the criteria of sustainability is an essential element of operating within the regenerative capacity of the ecosystem. The construction sector consumes enormous quantities of raw materials by weight (as much as 50 %), natural resources, energy and water, more than any other industrial sector. The built environment moreover, accounts for the largest share of greenhouse gas emissions (about 40 %) in terms of energy and usage. Human efforts for sustainable construction as well as environmental legislation such as Landfill Tax resulted in increased interest for eco-friendly composite materials. Eco-composites as an environmentally friendly construction materials address the priorities of the sustainable development, global changes and eco-systems, specifically focused on the point of sustainable energy systems (reduction of green-house gases and pollutant emissions). To be declared as an eco-friendly composite material, the composites should content natural fibres or resins, composed of waste material (post-consumer plastics/newspaper), to be biodegradable or easier to recycle. As a reinforcement, different natural plant-based fibres have been used: flax, hemp, sisal, jute, cellulose, kenaf, cotton. The list of polymers used as a matrix for eco-composites consist of natural (starch derivatives, cellulose, polyhydroxyalkanoates), semi-synthetic (polylactic acid) and synthetic (polycaprolactone, polyvinyl alcohol, polyolefins).

In the frame of this work, sustainability of several type of eco-composites, based on biodegradable (PHBV, PLLA) and recyclable (PP) polymer matrices reinforced with Rice husks and Kenaf fibres will be discussed and presented. Recyclability of the eco-composites was confirmed by their successful

recycling and incorporation as a filler in polymer mortars. In order to improve the final mechanical properties of the composites and to solve the problem of compatibilization in the studied eco-composites, promotion of a reactive interface between matrix and fibres was used. Characterization protocol of the obtained eco-composites included thermal, mechanical and morphological tests, as well as calculation and presentation of eco-indicators of the studied eco-composites. The results show that the best mechanical properties were found using the compatibilizing agent in all studied systems.

Besides conventional eco-friendly composites, in this work “self-reinforced cellulose” or “all-cellulose” (ACC) composites based on two cotton textile preforms (wovens and knits) will be discussed also. All-cellulose composites with ~95% fibre volume fraction were successfully prepared by the method of partial dissolution of fibre surfaces in 8 % (wt./v) LiCl/DMAc solvent. The thermal, mechanical and structural properties of the all-cellulose cotton-based composites were tested. By SEM microscopy, the composite morphology was studied. It was found that a dissolution time of 24 h lead to bio-based materials with the best overall mechanical performance, as this time allowed for the dissolution of a sufficient amount of fibre surface to obtain good interfacial bonding between fibres, while keeping a considerable amount of remaining fibre cores that provide a strong reinforcement to the composite.

Keywords: Sustainability Eco-composites Natural fibers Biodegradable matrices

5-HMF Based Polymers

Miroslav Huskić

Faculty of Polymer Technology, Ozare 19, Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

*miroslav.huskic@ftpo.eu

ABSTRACT

The world production of plastic materials is about 370 million tons. The vast majority of these materials are made from petroleum, whose reserves are limited. Besides, the use of plastics generates huge amounts of waste that pollutes the environment. Therefore, more and more research are being carried out worldwide with the aim of preparing plastics from renewable resources. The chemical decomposition of cellulose, the most common renewable carbon source on the planet, can provide raw materials for the production of various valuable molecules and bio-based polymers. One of the most desirable and potentially useful degradation products of cellulose is 5 HMF, from which several extremely useful chemicals can be obtained. 5 HMF is also the basis for the synthesis of polyethylene furanoate (PEF), which is a bio-based and in many respects better, substitute for polyethylene terephthalate (PET). Figures show some potential monomers which can be produced from 5 HMF.

In this lecture, the synthesis of several monomers and polymers based on 5 HMF will be presented with an emphasis on a new polymer based on phenol-5 HMF resin and its bio composites with paper.

Keywords: 5 HMF phenol bio-composite mechanical properties

POSTER SECTION

NANOmaterials

Application of Pyrophyllite, Titanium Dioxide and UV LED Light for Enhanced Disinfection

Altijana Hromić-Jahjefendić, Adna Hrapović, Selma Kozarić

Genetics and Bioengineering, International University of Sarajevo, Hrasnička cesta 15 Ilidža, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*ahromic@ius.edu.ba

ABSTRACT

Door handles can be a source of many dangerous bacteria and viruses, therefore regular disinfection is required. The exposure of toxic chemicals that are included in cleaning products and surface disinfectants can seriously harm the health of humans, causing breathing difficulties, skin irritations, rashes, hormonal imbalance and trigger antimicrobial resistance that can lead to worldwide health issues and infections. Pyrophyllite is abundantly present in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and due to its widespread application and abilities it can be integrated in applications which test the antibacterial properties of the mineral. Titanium dioxide has also emerged as a highly effective UV photocatalyst for environmental purification, demonstrating remarkable efficacy in surface disinfection and even as a carrier for drug delivery at the nanoparticle level. This project explores the antibacterial properties of pyrophyllite when utilized alongside UV LED light, as well as the synergistic effects of titanium dioxide and pyrophyllite under similar conditions. The specially designed door handle has an integrated UV LED source which passes through the pyrophyllite and titanium dioxide solutions, providing efficient hand disinfection without harming the skin microbiome. The door handle emits UV LED light for ten seconds, which is more than enough for the disinfection process to occur. The results show that total average of colony-forming units in a control sample was 137.86 before disinfection treatment, after the treatment with pyrophyllite solution the colony forming units reduced to the total average of 97.5 or by 29.5%, when distilled water is included in the pyrophyllite solution the efficiency percent is 55.04% which means that the colony forming units reduced to an average of 66.12. Pyrophyllite in combination with titanium dioxide reduced the colony forming units by 58.52% or to a total average of 57.18, and with distilled water it had the efficacy of 52.54% which means that it reduced the average of colony forming units to 66.43. The numerical data indicates that the pyrophyllite and titanium dioxide solution has the best efficiency in disinfecting the bacterial units and therefore can be used as a powerful disinfecting agent. By leveraging this technology, bacterial spread can be prevented, thereby safeguarding human health with a product suitable for everyday use.

Keywords: Pyrophyllite Titanium dioxide Disinfection UV LED

Graphical abstract:

Diving into the Stabilizing Mechanism of In-promoted Catalysts for the Sustainable Hydrogen Production: A Combined Operando XRD/XAS and Modeling Study

Filippo Bossola^{1*}, Mauro Coduri², Thantip Roongcharoen³, Martina Fracchia², Soroosh Saeedi¹, Xuan Trung Nguyen³, Claudio Evangelisti³, Dragos Stoian⁴, Luca Sementa⁵, Alessandro Fortunelli³, Vladimiro Dal Santo¹

¹CNR-SCITEC, Via Golgi 19 - 20133, Milano, Italy

²University of Pavia, Department of Chemistry, Viale Taramelli 16 - 27100, Pavia, Italy

³CNR-ICCOM, Via Moruzzi 1 - 56124, Pisa, Italy

⁴ESRF, Swiss Norwegian Beamlines, Grenoble 38000, France

⁵CNR-IPCF, Via Moruzzi 1 - 56124, Pisa, Italy

*filippo.bossola@cnr.it

ABSTRACT

Indium has demonstrated in the last years to be a remarkable promoter in reforming reactions for the hydrogen production by facilitating the water activation, and thus increasing the hydrogen selectivity, and by extending the catalysts lifetime due to an improved coke resistance. The latter action is critical to the development of robust catalysts, but the exact mechanism remains undisclosed. The results evidenced that, as expected, the monometallic Ni catalyst deactivated rather quickly not because of the oxidation of the Ni phase but rather due to the severe coke deposition in the form of carbon nanotubes and the detachment of the nanoparticles from the supporting material (Figure 1a). On the contrary, among a series of samples modified with In, the Ni-In(0.10) showed an extended lifetime of about 5 times the Ni monometallic counterpart (Figure 1b). Interestingly, the catalytic profile can be divided in a first phase whereby In formed a thermodynamically stable alloy Ni₃In (mixing energy below -5 eV). This alloy competes with C adsorption from the decomposition of acetic acid hence hampering the coke deposition. The same alloy, which eventually is displaced, hinders the catalyst restructuring from (100) and (111) to (311) facets, which in turn disfavours the production of carbon nanotubes as can be clearly seen in Figure 1b. After the consumption of the Ni₃In with time on stream, a second catalytic phase commenced. Despite a similar composition as the monometallic Ni catalyst, here the catalyst was still more durable, likely due to the more favourable Ni nanoparticle structure and facet exposure. The catalyst finally deactivated due to coke building up in the reactor. To note that the same stabilization was not limited to Ni and acetic acid; in fact, also Ru and glycerol steam reforming reaction enjoyed the same stabilization action exerted by the In modification.

Keywords: hydrogen steam reforming indium operando XRD/XAS

Graphene Oxide Membrane for Metal Ion Separation

Dragana Stević^{1*}, Sunčica Sukur², Radovan Kukobat³, Predrag Ilić⁴, Francesco Sirio Fumagalli⁵, Andrea Valsesia⁵, Pascal Colpo⁵ and Svetlana Popović¹

¹Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Boulevar cara Lazara 1, Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute of Molecular and Translational Medicine, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, Palacky University Olomouc, Hněvotínská 5, 779 00 Olomouc, Czech Republic

³Faculty of Technology, Department of Chemical Engineering and Technology, University of Banja Luka, B.V Stepe Stepanovica 73, 78000 Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

⁴Institute for Protection and Ecology of the Republic of Srpska, 78000 Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

⁵Directorate General Joint Research Centre, Directorate F – Health and Food – Technologies for Health (F.2), via Fermi 2749, 21027 ISPRA (VA), Italy

*dragana.stevic@pmf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

Developing graphene oxide (GO) membranes for metal ions separation has been extensively studied during the last decade. The new membrane that can efficiently separate the metal ions from water such as water contaminated with metal ions after washing the landfill soil is still challenging. This presentation will show the method for washing the landfill soil using water and hydrochloric acid. The soil were collected from the landfill of Bijeljina region and treated using ultrasonic treatment and mixing to separate the metal ions from the minerals and organic matter. The metal cations of Cd (II), Zn (II) and Pb (II) were separated from the soil and their separation was further investigated by GO membranes. The GO membranes were prepared by vacuum filtration on the polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) membrane whose pore size was 0.5 μm in diameter. After vacuum filtration of GO dispersion, a thin layer of the GO membrane of $\sim 0.7 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness was formed. Water contaminated with metal ions was filtrated through the GO membrane at the transmembrane pressure difference of 102 Pa. Rejections of metal ions by GO membrane were 99.80 for Pb (II), 96.15 % for Cd (II), and 44.00 % for Zn (II) cations. The size of the Pb (II) cation is larger than that of Zn (II) and Cd (II), respectively. The metal cation separation mechanism was elucidated using molecular dynamics simulations. GO has nanowindows of $\sim 1\text{nm}$ on the basal planes, being available for entering and permeance of metal cations between the GO layers. The interlayer distance was adjusted to find the interlayer distance at which the Pb (II) cations can be rejected. Theoretically, the complete rejection of Pb (II) cation was achieved at the GO interlayer distance of 0.50 nm, owing to the size exclusion. Thus, the GO membrane is promising for further metal ion separation from wastewaters including landfill wastewaters.

Keywords:

Graphene oxide

Membrane

Rejection

Permeation

Soil washing

Application of Agro-Industrial Waste for Nanomaterial Synthesis

Nataša Slijepčević^{1*}, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović¹, Marijana Anđelić¹, Gabor Kozma², Dunja Rađenović¹, Slaven Tenodi¹, Đurđa Kerkez¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, Novi Sad, Republika Srbija

²University of Szeged, Interdisciplinary Excellence Centre, Department of Applied and Environmental Chemistry, Rerrich Béla tér 1, Szeged, H-6720, Hungary.

*natasa.slijepcevic@dh.uns.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

Nowadays the use of nanotechnology in environmental remediation, especially iron-based nanoparticles have been successfully performed because of their high specific surface area and reactivity. The PAL-nZVI (Phragmites australis-nano zero-valent iron) was synthesized in this paper using a common reed leaves-mediated single-step method with Fe^{3+} as precursors, indicating an environmentally friendly approach. The eco-friendly solvents like polyphenols in plant extracts act as the main precursors for formation and stability of nZVI in synthetic process. Synthesis of PAL-nZVI included collecting of common reed leaves from coastal area around Great Bačka Canal, Vojvodina, Serbia. The concentration of 60 g/L, has been chosen from previous research. The fine powder of leaves was placed in deionized water and heated to boiling for 1h. After cooling, the extract was centrifuged at 7000rpm for 20min, and supernatant filtered under vacuum filtration. For the production of nanoparticles mixture of common reed extract and 0.1M Fe(III)-chloride in ration 3:1 was used for preparation. The iron (III) solution was added drop wise to plant extract mixing on a magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The appearance of a black solution was a sign of the formation of iron NPs. The evaluation of the viability of PAL leaves to produce extract which is capable of reducing Fe^{3+} in aqueous solution was determined using FRAP method and total phenols, where results show good correlation with previous study. pH value of PAL-nZVI solution was acidic. At the isoelectric point (pHi), undissociated surface hydroxyl groups render the oxide surface neutrally charged. A low pHi value (4.0) for PAL-nZVI results from the high acidity of the PAL extract. UV-Vis spectra show distinctive absorption peaks, indicating the formation of PAL-nZVI. SEM and TEM micrographs reveal agglomerates of spherical PAL-nZVIs, approximately 30nm in size, with C, O, and Cl signals attributed to reed leaf phenolic compounds and iron(III) salt. XPS analysis confirms the elemental composition and agglomeration, suggesting the potential synthesis of PAL-nZVI from common reed leaves as agro-industrial waste.

Keywords:

nanomaterials

common reed

characterization

agro-industrial waste

Acknowledgement: The research was financed by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #7753609, BEuSED.

Electron Migration through Nanotubes Induced by Mechanical Deformation

Zoran P. Popović, Milan Damnjanović, Ivanka Milošević

NanoLab, Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade, Studentski trg 12, Belgrade, Serbia

*zokapop@ff.bg.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

Topological phase transition in semiconducting carbon nanotubes along with locally electrons shifting can be driven by applying realistic continual deformation. Homogeneous deformations are slow changes, being considered as adiabatic. Function of electron bands are changed as a consequence of continual reparametrization of Hamiltonian and overlap matrix elements, via homogeneous deformations. In the space of deformation and geometrical parameters exists a continual set of singular points which separate two topological phases, made of singular points. The occurrence of phase transition is followed by approaching two bands with the same angular momentum quantum number. They come closer at specific wavevector, becoming cone-like bands, but without touching, due to the non-crossing rule. When a singular point is crossed, electron migration occurs locally inside a monomer, via electron tunnelling from the centre of the monomer to its ends, but globally without crossing into the conduction zone. Appropriately chosen symmetry preserved deformations could trigger electron tunnelling, during the crossing between the topological phases. It occurs as a simultaneous shift of electron pairs along a cylinder. Due to the symmetry preserving, especially preserving the two-fold rotational axis U , two electrons from the monomer centre move in opposite directions toward the monomer ends. Amplitude of local current depends on the number of valence electrons (bands) and on the type and deformation intensity, also influencing the number of bands involved in phase transition. Applying a magnetic field breaks the symmetry, causing the transition through topological phases to occur by individual electrons jumping between neighboring monomers, rather than in locally polarized pairs. Localized alternating charge transfer and change of polarization are expected to be controlled via realistic values of periodic adiabatic homogeneous deformations which yield singular points line crossings.

Keywords: carbon nanotube symmetry Wilson loop deformations

Synthesis of Hydrophobic Zeolite from Ugljevik Thermal Power Plant Fly Ash

Tijana Kremenović¹, Nikolina Landeka^{1,*}, Martinez Eugénie², Gambacorti Narciso², Marija Stojaković¹

¹*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, Mladena Stojanovića 2 78000, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina*

²*Atomic Energy and Alternative Energies Commission, Laboratoire d'électronique des technologies de l'information, 17 avenue des Martyrs 38054, Grenoble, France*

*nikolina.landeka@student.pmf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

The proliferation of oil and petroleum spills poses significant environmental threats, necessitating the development of efficient remediation techniques. This study focuses on the synthesis of hydrophobic zeolites from fly ash, a widely available industrial byproduct, as a potential solution for mitigating waterborne oil contamination. Fly ash sample we used was supplied from the Ugljevik thermal power plant, one of the five existing power plants in Bosnia and Herzegovina. XPS analysis of fly ash showed that there are no metallic contaminants. All the elements typical for fly ash were detected except Ti, K and P. Through a novel synthesis approach, fly ash was transformed into hydrophobic zeolite materials with tailored surface properties optimized for oil sorption applications. Characterization techniques including Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) confirm the successful conversion of fly ash into zeolite structures and the introduction of hydrophobic functionalities. Sorption experiments conducted using one oil type demonstrate the superior performance of hydrophobic zeolites in rapidly and selectively adsorbing oil from aqueous environments, with high sorption capacities and excellent reusability. Furthermore, the synthesized materials exhibit enhanced buoyancy, facilitating their recovery from water surfaces post-spill cleanup operations. The environmentally benign nature of fly ash-based zeolite synthesis offers a sustainable and cost-effective approach for addressing oil spill incidents while concurrently valorising industrial waste. This research contributes to the advancement of eco-friendly strategies for environmental remediation and underscores the potential of hydrophobic zeolites derived from fly ash as a promising technology for oil spill containment and cleanup efforts.

Keywords: Fly ash Zeolite Oil spills Adsorption

Co-sputtered Cu and Ti Coating in O₂ Atmosphere

Maria P. Nikolova^{1*}, I. Tsvetkov¹, Y Handzhiyski², Margarita D. Apostolova²

¹A. Kanchev University of Ruse "A. Kanchev", Dept. Department of Material Science and Technology, 8 Studentska Str., 7017 Ruse, Bulgaria

²Roumen Tsanev Institute of Molecular Biology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 21, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

*mpnikolova@uni-ruse.bg

ABSTRACT

S mosaic target material of titanium (Ti) and copper (Cu) was used to deposit CuO/TiO₂ coatings on Ti₆Al₄V alloy. The aim was to examine the change in composition, structure and adhesion of the deposited films on titanium alloy when varying the titanium/copper (20:1, 41:1, 179:1, 418:1 and 837:1) ratio of the target material. The coatings were obtained by sputtering in a glow-discharge in a pure O₂ atmosphere for a deposition time of 240 min. All coatings showed homogenous Cu distribution and the film thickness decreased with the reduction of Cu content in the composite target. Cu content in the coatings followed a power function of decrease with reduction of Ti-Cu content in the target while the increase of Ti showed logarithmic dependence. In all coatings, anatase and rutile TiO₂ phases were detected whereas Cu atoms participated only in the formation of monoclinic CuO. TiO₂-rich coatings demonstrated better adhesion to the Ti₆Al₄V alloy, whereas the critical loads of CuO-rich films were dependent on coating thickness.

At 179:1 ratio, different substrate values, selected from 0 to -150 V, were used in the process. The increase in bias voltage from -50 to -150 V decreased the thickness of the oxide coatings and improved their adhesion to the substrate while increasing the Cu₂O phase at the expense of a CuO phase decrease. Simultaneously, the increase in bias voltage decreased Cu content from about 32 wt% for the -50 V biased down to around 11 wt% for the -150 V biased specimens. The antimicrobial efficacy against E. coli estimated by direct contact experiments on the top of the uncoated (control) and coated Ti₆Al₄V alloy revealed about 94% inhibition for the -50V biased down to around 37% for the -150 V biased coatings as opposed to the control.

Keywords: PVD coatings Cu-doped TiO₂ antibacterial

Sample	Ti6Al4V	Coated 0 V	Coated -50 V	Coated -100 V	Coated -150 V
CFU	332±5	53±5	19±7	30±6	204±8
%R towards Ti6Al4V	-	84	94	91	37
%R towards 0V	-	-	64	43	-285

The Possibility of Using Nanomaterials for the Remediation of Soil Contaminated with Toxic Metals

Željko Todorović¹, Svetlana Ilić¹, Sonja Marković¹, Predrag Ilić^{1,*}

*PSRI Institute for Protection and Ecology of the Republic of Srpska, Vidovdanska 43,
Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina*

*predrag.ilic@institutzei.net

ABSTRACT

Toxic metal contamination in soil presents a severe environmental and health hazard due to the toxic, persistent, and bioaccumulative nature of these metals. In the Zvornik-Bijeljina region various illegal dumpsites and the Incel industrial site (Banja Luka), soil samples have revealed alarming concentrations of toxic metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), and nickel (Ni). For example, lead concentrations reached up to 3423 mg/kg, cadmium up to 297 mg/kg, and nickel up to 818 mg/kg, significantly exceeding permissible limits. These elevated levels highlight the urgent need for effective remediation strategies to mitigate the adverse effects on human health and the environment. Our research identifies significant contamination levels at these sites, necessitating immediate intervention. Traditional remediation techniques have proven insufficient, prompting the exploration of advanced methods. Among these, nanotechnology emerges as a particularly effective solution. Nanomaterials such as nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI), magnesium oxide (MgO) nanoparticles, and graphene oxide exhibit high surface area and reactivity, enabling efficient adsorption, reduction, and stabilization of toxic metals in soils. These nanomaterials can transform toxic metals into less harmful forms, thereby reducing their bioavailability and mobility. Additionally, combining nanotechnology with geotextiles and clay layers, particularly bentonite, enhances the remediation process. Geotextiles impregnated with nanomaterials create barriers that adsorb toxic metals and prevent their leaching into groundwater. Bentonite clay, known for its high cation exchange capacity, adsorbs toxic metals and stabilizes them over time, ensuring their long-term immobilization and reducing environmental risks.

Keywords: Toxic metals Remediation Geotextile Nanomaterial

Green Microemulsion Synthesis of the Manganese Oxide Nanoparticles

Tatjana Baljak^{1,*}, Sanja Kubat¹, Smiljana Paraš² and Suzana Gotovac Atlagić¹

¹University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Chemistry Department, Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000, Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Biology Department, Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000, Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*tatjana.baljak@student.pmf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

Manganese oxide nanoparticles are highly applicable in a number of applications. For example, making batteries, decolorizing glass, for medical purposes, as catalysts, etc.

Synthesis methods might be different and are classified into two groups: bottom-up (sol-gel method, pyrolysis, chemical vapor deposition, and biosynthesis) and top-down (mechanical grinding, laser ablation, and thermal decomposition).

The present paper was realized in Bosnia and Herzegovina which has a small manganese ore mine extracting around 40 000 tonnes yearly. This paper presents the synthesis of manganese oxide nanoparticles using "green" emulsifiers. In this method, only plant extracts, which are considered waste (weeds), are collected, which is still a rarely used approach. These types of plants were used for reasons to preserve the environment and human health, without the use of toxic chemicals, and also to reduce the consumption of medicinal plants for these purposes, because they have a very important role in medicine.

Characterization of the obtained nanoparticles by OM and XRD will be shown and results appropriately discussed.

Keywords: Manganese oxide Synthesis "Green" emulsion Weeds

POSTER SECTION
POLYmers

Amino-functionalized Glycidyl Methacrylate-based Copolymer as an Effective Sorbent for Anionic Dye from Aqueous Solutions

Zvezdana P. Sandić¹, Tamara T. Tadić², Sandra S. Bulatović², Natalija Ž. Nedić², Aleksandra B. Nastasović², Bojana M. Marković^{2,*}

¹University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Natural Science and Mathematics, Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000 Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, B&H

²University of Belgrade - Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

*bojana.markovic@ihtm.bg.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

The dyes, which are extensively utilized in industries such as textile, leather, food, printing, and cosmetics, pose serious environmental contaminants due to their high toxicity and carcinogenicity. Therefore, the removal of the dyes from wastewater before its discharge is crucial for environmental quality improvement. A variety of technologies such as chemical coagulation, flocculation, photodegradation, reverse osmosis, membrane separation, biological treatment, and sorption have been used for the treatment of dye-contaminated waters. Sorption is deemed the most effective and simplest method for treating polluted waters. Among the wide variety of sorbents, polymers with adjustable surface chemistry and high specific surface areas have attracted a lot of attention as sorbents in the environmental protection field. In the present research, amino-functionalized macroporous glycidyl methacrylate-based copolymer, pSGE-DA, was synthesized by a ring-opening reaction of the pendant epoxy groups of poly(glycidyl methacrylate-co-ethylene glycol dimethacrylate) with diamine and used for removal of Eriochrome violet B (ECV), as a model anionic dye pollutant, from aqueous solutions. The morphology and surface chemistry of pSGE-DA were determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and pHPZC analysis. The effect of sorbent dose (4 - 20 g/L) and initial dye concentration (10 - 50 ppm) on sorption capacity was examined. All experiments were done in batch static non-competitive conditions, at the unadjustable pH value of dye solutions, an agitation of 450 rpm, and room temperature. The sorption mechanism was investigated using the Langmuir, Freundlich, and Temkin isotherms models. The results suggest the monolayer sorption and homogeneous distribution of active sites on pSGE-DA sorbent. The maximal sorption capacity was 16.8 mg/g. The porous pSGE-DA sorbent displayed more than 98% ECV uptake from an aqueous solution, underlining the great potential this sorbent possesses for the removal of anionic dyes from contaminated waters.

Keywords: Glycidyl methacrylate Porous copolymer Sorption Anionic dye

Kaolin from Bosnia and Herzegovina as Potential Material in Synthesis of Geopolymers

Anja Dujković¹, Dragan Gvozdrenović^{2*}, Ferenc Madai³, Viktor Madai⁴, Marija Stojaković⁵

*Chemistry Department, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka,
Bosnia and Herzegovina*

*dragan.gvozdrenovic@student.pmf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

Geopolymers are considered great influencers of modern engineering. They consist of aluminosilicates. Kaolin clay found in these geopolymers is found locally in Bosnia and Herzegovina. There is a huge potential for exploitation of kaolin clay in Bosnia, so there is a huge potential of producing geopolymers. Kaolin is a soft clay, formed from silicates via mineral decomposition—the chemical properties of kaolin ensure its wide usage in the pharmaceuticals and construction industry. For the synthesis of geopolymers, the following substances were used: calcinated kaolin, NaOH, and glass water. Characterization was done using: OM, FTIR, and BET. FTIR indicated vibrations at $\sim 960\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to Si—O—Si and Si—O vibrations. OM showed the crystalline agglomerates. BET analysis confirmed that a mesoporous material with a large specific surface area. The specific surface is $700,125\text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$. Synthesized geopolymer showed great mechanical, and physical properties. Therefore, this geopolymer could be applied in many fields from construction to technical. Figure attached shows a) Photo of kaolin geopolymer taken by Optical Microscope, b) Kaolin from the deposit after the process of separation, c) and d) Photos of the deposit located in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Keywords: kaolin geopolymer

Separation of Cu-ions from Mixed Polymer Fraction of Recycled Electric Cables

Anđela Korica¹, Milica Kosić¹, Suzana Gotovac-Atlagić¹, Anita Grozdanov^{2*}

¹Chemistry Department, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka, Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000 Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²Department of Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University Ss Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, Rugjer Boskovic 16, 1000 Skopje, North Macedonia

*anita@tmf.ukim.edu.mk

ABSTRACT

In the last few decades an increase in waste materials has been observed and researchers have been trying to find a new use for them, whether through recycling or simply finding new applications. Electronic industry is one of the leading fields by the number of consumers and therefore the waste produced greatly varies in the materials it includes. EEC reported for 2015, recycling of insulated wires and cable scraps overpassed 3,5 million metric tons with 2,5 million of which classified as recoverable waste. LCA of scraps generated from wire and cable industry estimated 30.75 tons of CO₂ equivalents which could be avoided if plastic scrap recycling was incorporated into LCA of cable materials. Copper wiring waste, which is the main topic of this research, is mostly a mixture of polymeric mass and left-over Copper wires after the primary process of mechanical separation. The yearly production of Copper wiring waste in the world amounts to 9,85 million tons. The material used in this research is acquired from a recycling company in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Prizma). It is a mechanically crushed mixture of polymer mass and Copper wires.

The primary problem in this technique is that a great amount of Cu is trapped in the polymeric mass. This research tries to extract trapped Cu from the polymeric mass through the process of complexation with different Ammonia-ion salts. Cu that is extracted can be further used as a raw material, especially since there is a deficit in the natural reserves. However, the application of the leftover polymeric mass is still a researchable field. Some of the proposed applications are as a filler in the construction industry or the process of pyrolysis with the goal of producing active carbon.

Keywords: Copper wires Polymeric mass Ammonia-ion salts Complexation

The Contribution of Modern Production to the Sustainable Development

Brankica Todorović

Faculty of contemporary arts, Svetozara Miletica no. 7, Belgrade, Serbia

*brankica.todorovic@fsu.edu.rs

ABSTRACT

Modern production which uses ecological materials, technology and processes, affects to reduced environmental pollution. By using ecological materials, such as, polymer materials based on fossil or renewable raw materials, significant savings in energy and raw materials can be achieved and contribute to sustainable development.

Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) define guidelines within three dimensions of sustainable development: economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection. SDG 12: Responsible consumption and production aim to ensure sustainable patterns of consumption and production. The effectiveness in achieving SDG 12 is analysed using indicators: material footprint, domestic material consumption per inhabitant, resource productivity and national waste recycling rate. SDG 9: Industry, innovation, infrastructure, contains the indicator of CO₂ emissions per unit of added value.

In the process of accession to the EU, the Republic of Serbia should to fulfil obligations under Chapter 27: Environment and Climate Change, which are also related, to the segment of industrial pollution. The objectives of the research in the paper are:

1. Analysis of indicators of SDG 9 and 12 and assessment of achieved progress,
2. Fulfilment of the obligations of the Republic of Serbia in the EU accession process in the segment of industrial pollution and
3. Overview of key segments of industrial production and industrial policy that contribute to the achievement of the SDG.

Keywords: Agenda 2030 SDG Ecological materials Industry production

Decrease in Diameter of Synthetic Fibers as a Threatening Factor in Microplastics Pollution

Milica Balaban¹, Dejana Savić¹, Dragana Gajić¹, Suzana Gotovac Atlagić¹, Nakanishi Tadashi² and Sanja Pržulj^{1,*}

¹Chemistry Department, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka, Mladena Stojanovića 2, 78000 Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²Retired professor at: Faculty of Core Research, Natural Science Division, Ochanomizu University, 2-1-1 Otsuka, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

*sanja.sehovac@pmf.unibl.org

ABSTRACT

The presence of microplastics in all environmental spheres has become one of the most investigated problems nowadays. Hyperproduction of polymers, which in the last decades reached their maximum, led to massive plastic litter deposition. Recognition of the threats by microplastics and nanoplastics became the focus of scientific observations only in the last decade. This kind of pollutant can be described as solid particles with high polymer content, with a size of 5 mm or less, insoluble in water. Based on the shape, microplastics can be found in the environment as microbeads, fibers, fragments, film foam pellets, and filaments. When mentioning filaments, also the micro and nanofibers come to the attention of the scientific community and this form is the subject of the present review poster. Both particles and fibers experience continuous degradation in the water environment which brings changes in their properties like color, the morphology of surface, size, crystallinity, and density, thus also impacting their chemical and physical activities, changing the level of the threat they pose to the environments and living organisms. Dramatic data, especially from the last few years, proves the presence of microplastics in soil, water, air sources, marine organisms, salt, beer, and even bottled drinking water. In the 1950s, large-scale plastic production commenced with an output of two million tons. Over the last two decades, global plastic production has nearly doubled, reaching 390.7 million tons in 2021. It is projected that worldwide plastic production will reach 1.1 billion tons by 2050. There are numerous studies on their accumulation in animal and human tissue and body parts, altering the immune system and causing other clinical complications. Micro and nanofibers are especially hard to control due to the extensive laundry process both in households and in the textile industry as well. Present paper aims at emphasizing the threats coming from the increasing finer fibres. Namely, paradox is that on one hand, decreasing the diameters and producing ever finer fibres, helps avoid hard labour necessary for production of natural fibres. Also, finer synthetic fibres have also much more applications or in the case of clothing, more pleasant touch. However, when they find the way to the aqueous environment or to the respiratory organs in humans and animals, consequences such as tissue inflammation and subsequent genotoxicity need to be addressed.

Keywords: microplastics fibers pollution

The background is a solid orange color with several thin, dark orange, wavy lines that create a sense of movement and depth. The lines are irregular and organic in shape, resembling liquid or smoke. The text is positioned in the lower right quadrant of the page.

**Conference
supporters**

European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) EIT Raw Materials Knowledge Innovation Community (KIC) EIT Manufacturing KIC

EIT is the association, which represents Europe's largest innovation network strengthening innovation since 2008. Their mission is to create jobs and deliver sustainable and smart growth. EIT is an integral part of Horizon Europe, the EU's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. It drives innovation by bringing together organisations across business, education, and research. The goal of these partnerships is to find and commercialise solutions to pressing global challenges. For each global challenge, there is an ecosystem of partnerships called Knowledge and Innovation Communities. To face these global challenges, EIT community of partners offers a wide range of education courses, business creation and acceleration services, and innovation-driven research projects.

Pillar 3 of Horizon Europe is 'Innovative Europe' in which EIT come in as contributor. With budget of EUR 3 billion, EIT is strengthening sustainable innovation ecosystems across Europe, fostering the development of entrepreneurial and innovation skills in a lifelong learning perspective, supporting EU universities in integrating more entrepreneurial education, bringing new solutions to global societal challenges to the market, creating synergies and added value within Horizon Europe.

EIT RawMaterials is a key European actor established in 2015 to advance Europe's transition into a sustainable economy. EIT RawMaterials overarching mandate is to support securing the supply of critical raw materials to the European industry by driving innovation along the raw materials value chain. EIT RawMaterials builds on the world's largest network of partners in raw materials and advanced materials. EIT RawMaterials mission is to develop raw materials into a major strength for Europe by boosting competitiveness, growth and attractiveness of the European raw materials sector via radical innovation, new education approaches and guided entrepreneurship.

This year NanoPol conference was supported through the EIT HEI Initiative, which is a joint activity of the EIT community, which recognises higher education institutions (HEIs) as the pivotal actors in regional and European innovation ecosystems. NanoPol 2024 conference represented the final event of the DeepGreenInno project, code: 23447.

EIT HEI Initiative enhanced the innovation capacity and entrepreneurial mindset of HEIs involved in DeepGreenInno project and fostered their innovation capabilities in deep tech. Consortium and organising committee of the conference thank the EIT broader community very much for this support.

Ministry of Scientific Research Development and Higher Education of Republic of Srpska

Support of the scientific and educational activities in Bosnia and Herzegovina are managed at the entity levels. University of Banja Luka thus, as the state university, receives its support from the Ministry for Scientific and Technological Development and Higher Education of Republika Srpska. This Ministry performs administrative and other professional tasks related to: scientific and technological development and improvement of higher education, as well as the development and monitoring of strategies in the aforementioned areas. With a number of modest, yet continuous support schemes, Ministry is aiming to improve and encourage the development of fundamental developmental applied research. In addition, they are encouraging innovation and economic development with new technologies.

In the field of higher education and student standards, they play an important role and are constantly making efforts to improve those. Verification and equivalence of foreign higher education diplomas and compliance of educational policy with global technological trends helps in bringing international educational practices into the Republic.

Ministry supports promotion of the use of new technologies and it performs administrative supervision in the field of information and communication technologies.

Funding scheme of the Ministry includes: support to the thematic scientific projects, support to the preparation and participation in the international projects, support to the industrial collaboration, periodic support to the best papers published in the peer-reviewed and indexed international journals, support to the capacity building of the laboratories, competitions for the best technological innovation and many more. Ministry aims as increasing its budget in the years to follow and try to raise the percent of GDP given to science and higher education.

NanoPol conference is being recognized and endorsed by the Ministry. The Conference received the financial support from the Ministry two years in a row through the small-scale projects number: 19.032/966-79/22 and 19.032/966-66/23. The organizing and scientific committee thank the Ministry and express their dedication to increasing the quality of the conference in each following year.

COST Association (European Cooperation in Science and Technology)

COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) is a funding organisation for research and innovation networks. Our Actions help connect research initiatives across Europe and beyond and enable researchers and innovators to grow their ideas in any science and technology field by sharing them with their peers. COST Actions are bottom-up networks with a duration of four years that boost research, innovation and careers.

Number of the COST has its special tool for further networking, which is called COST participation in external events (<https://www.cost.eu/events/>). Not only through the regular tools such as COST Academy, COST Action events, COST Connect but also by holding its promo sessions at different events on scientific events organized through other schemes in different countries, COST is aiming at spreading the word about its activities.

COST association held its promo stands at the NanoPol2023 also this year at NanoPol2024. Both years, support was given through the thematic COST-coffee break and extensive promotional printed materials, where the stand promoters were former or present participants at the COST actions.

Organising and Scientific committee of NanoPol2024 thanks the COST association for this support and expresses satisfaction by this added value to the conference and valuable information given to our participants about possibilities of networking throughout European scientific / professional community.

